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CHARACTERIZATION OF NANO-SCALE PARTICLE DERIVED FROM DICALCIUM PHOSPHATE (DCPD) AND LEAD ION

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Dicalcium phosphate dihydrate (DCPD, $\text{CaHPO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$) has been recognized for its ability to react with fluoride ions to form stable fluorapatite (FAp, $\text{Ca}_{10}(\text{PO}_4)_6\text{F}_2$), suggesting its potential to stabilize hazardous elements in the environment. Lead immobilization by apatite systems is typically explained by the substitution of calcium ions in hydroxyapatite (HAp) with lead ions, forming lead-substituted hydroxyapatite (Pb-HAp, $\text{Ca}_{10-x}\text{Pb}_x(\text{PO}_4)_6(\text{OH})_2$). This study aimed to investigate whether DCPD can stabilize Pb^{2+} through similar mechanisms. Aqueous solutions with varying Pb^{2+} concentrations were prepared and reacted with DCPD under shaking (80 rpm, 24 h). The resulting solids were collected via membrane filtration (0.45 μm) and analyzed using X-ray diffraction (XRD), field-emission scanning electron microscopy (FE-SEM), energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS), and inductively coupled plasma atomic emission spectroscopy (ICP-AES). The results showed that DCPD effectively reduced Pb^{2+} concentrations in solution. Two types of needle-like morphologies were observed in the solid phase. EDS analysis indicated that these particles contained no calcium, suggesting the formation of hydroxypyromorphite (HPY, $\text{Pb}_{10}(\text{PO}_4)_6(\text{OH})_2$), rather than Pb-HAp. Under low Pb^{2+} conditions, minor phases of HAp and octacalcium phosphate (OCP, $\text{Ca}_8\text{H}_2(\text{PO}_4)_6 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$) were also detected, likely precipitated from calcium and phosphate ions released from DCPD in acidic conditions. These findings suggest that DCPD participates in phase transformations involving Pb^{2+} and may contribute to lead immobilization. The formation of HPY highlights a promising pathway for further investigation into DCPD-based remediation strategies.

Keywords: Calcium phosphate, Apatite, Lead, Nano-hybridization

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